

VARIETAL SCREENING AND COMPARATIVE TOXICITY OF SOME PLANT EXTRACTS FOR CONTROL OF *Fusarium* WILT OF GROUNDNUT (*Arachis hypogaea* L).

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ABSTRACT

Three varieties of groundnut RMP 12, Mbaise Large, and Samnut 23 as well as leaf extracts of *Denettia tripetala*, *Spondias mombin*, *benomyl* and sterile distilled water were screened for their effects against *Fusarium oxysporium*, causal agent of *Fusarium* wilt of groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) in the greenhouse. The seeds were sown in 4kg heat sterilized top soil contained in 20cm diameter pots. The pots were arranged in 3 x 4 factorial; in a randomized complete block design (RCBD). Two weeks after planting (2 WAP), the seedlings were inoculated by injection of 3ml (10^5 spores/ml) strength suspension at the bases of the seedlings and left in a humid chamber. RMP 12 had the best fresh weight and dry matter yield which was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) superior to other varieties, an indication that it could be the most tolerant to the disease. However, *Denettia tripetala* and *benomyl* treated seedlings significantly reduced the severity of the wilt disease better than *Spondias mombin*. Hence RMP 12 variety and extracts of *D. tripetala* should be used in IPM programmes by resource- poor farmers in the management of *Fusarium* wilt disease of groundnut.

Keywords: Plant extracts, *Denettia tripetala*, *Fusarium oxysporium*, IPM.

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INTRODUCTION

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L) (Family, *Fabaceae*) is an important annual oil seed crop and grain legume, originally domesticated in South and Central America as well as Mexico. The seed contains 50% oil, 25-30% protein, 20% carbohydrate and 5% fibre and ash (Fageria *et al.*, 1997). The crop is consumed as whole seeds while the haulms are fed livestock or incorporated into soils as green manure. The crop also plays a soil fertility restorative role in farming systems through nodular fixation of atmospheric nitrogen (Hassain *et al.*, 2005), making the crop adaptive to a wide range of soils (Tranthithu, 2003). Worldwide 29.5 million metric tonnes of groundnuts are produced annually and Nigeria is the world's fourth largest producer contributing 1.51 million metric tonnes (Soyatech, 2011). Groundnut is one of the most popular commerce crops in Nigeria providing up to 20% of Nigeria's total export earnings in the 1970s and contributing significantly to the diets and incomes of small holder farmers (Lombin and Adeleke, 1988).

Fusarium wilt induced by *Fusarium oxysporium* cause a lot of damage in groundnut. Affected plants show drooping of leaves, chlorosis and eventual death. The disease is more severe in late cases than in early ones and seeds harvested from infected plants are duller in appearance (Havere and Nene, 1980). Control of this disease is by the use of Benlate and Dithane M45 for seed or foliar interventions. However, due to the associated drawbacks of synthetic chemicals for pest control such as mammalian toxicity, pathogen resistance and resurgence, effects on non-target species and eco-non degradability, alternatives are being sought (Okwu *et al.*, 2007, Enyiukwu and Awurum, 2011). One such alternative is the use of plant extracts in plant disease control.

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Many workers have reported the efficacy of extracts of higher plants in the control of fungal diseases of crops (Amadioha, 2003; Awurum *et al.*, 2005). These plant materials are readily available in the farming localities of the tropics, cheap and eco-degradable.

Therefore this present work focuses on evaluating the fungitoxic effects of *Dennetia tripetala* and *Spondias mombin* on the severity of *Fusarium* wilt of groundnut caused by *Fusarium oxysporium* and the performance of three varieties of the crop when challenged by the pathogen.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sources of seeds and plant materials

The experiment was conducted in the greenhouse of the Department of Plant Health Management of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Nigeria in 2011. The seeds of 3 varieties of groundnut Mbaise large (a local variety), Samnut 23, and RMP 12 collected from the Institute for Agricultural Research, Samaru, Zaria Nigeria and leaves of *Dennetia tripetala* and *Spondias mombin* collected from the University neighbourhood were used for the study.

Isolation of Inoculum

Seeds of the three groundnut varieties were collected from infested fields of the University Research Farm. The seeds were surface-sterilized in 70% alcohol for 1 minute and then rinsed in several changes of sterile distilled water. The seeds were then plated in a Petri dish containing moistened whatman No 1 filter paper, covered and incubated for 7 days at 27°C. Thereafter, 200g of fresh peeled potato were boiled in 1000ml of sterile distilled water in a 2L feat bottomed flask. The broth was sieved through 4-folds of sterile cheese cloth into another clean 2L flat bottomed flask to which 20g glucose and 15g agar were added, stoppered and autoclaved for 30 minutes at 15 Psi. Using a flamed needle, bits of the organism that grew out of the incubated seeds were transferred on PDA thus prepared contained in Petri dishes and sub-cultured repeatedly till pure culture of the organism was obtained. The organism was placed on a slide and observed under a microscope and its identity confirmed to be *Fusarium oxysporium* by the aid of identification manual by Barnett and Hunter (1983).

Preparation of extracts

Leaves of *D. tripetala* and *S. mombin* were air dried on a laboratory bench for 10 days. They were then milled into powder using an electric blender. The powders were stored differently in air tight bottles until required.

Twenty (20) grams of each powder were soaked differently in 250 ml beaker containing 100ml of sterile distilled water, allowed to stand for 1 hour and then sieved through 4-folds of sterile cheese cloth to obtain 20% filtrates of the plant materials respectively. The filtrates thus prepared were used to spray the inoculated seedlings.

Planting/plant inoculation

Seeds were sown in 20cm diameter plastic pots, containing 4kg heat sterilized soil. The loam-rich soil was sterilized in a sack suspended over 20L of water in a cut drum and heated to 100°C for 4 hours. The seeds were sown 2 per pot and later thinned to 1 seedling after sprouting. The soil was kept moist throughout the experiment. The seedlings were inoculated by injection of 3ml of the spore suspension of the pathogen prepared by lifting 60cm² agar of 10-day old culture stock of the pathogen in 200ml of sterile distilled water contained in a beaker; and standardizing the suspension to 10⁵ spores/ml using a haemocytometer, into the base of each seedling. The seedlings were covered with light transparent polythene bags for 48 hours to maintain the right humidity that allows the pathogen to grow. The experiment was arranged in a 3 x 4 factorial in an RCBD layout.

The disease severely score was recorded by visual assessment of the inoculated seedlings on a 6-point scale using the formula by Allen *et al.*, (1981) as:

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- O = No symptoms
- 1 = Wilt on less than 20% of leaves
- 2 = Wilt on less than half of leaves
- 3 = Wilt on up to 60% of leaves
- 4 = Wilt on most of leaves
- 5 = Wilt heavy leading to death of seedling

Statistical analysis

Data collected from 3 weeks after plating were analyzed by analysis of variance (ANOVA) and means separated by Fishers Least Significant Difference (F – LSD) at 0.05 level of probability.

RESULTS

The results show that the extracts had significant effects on the disease severity of the various varieties of *Arachis hypogaea*. In terms of varieties RMP 12 had the least disease severity of 2.01 while Mbaise large had the highest severity of 3.86 (Table 1).

The results also indicate that there were significant differences among the disease severity scores on plants subjected to the various treatments. Benomyl treated plants were significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) superior in reducing the severity of the wilt disease on the test crops with score of 2.28 than extracts treated plants while sterile water treated plants had the highest mean severity score of 3.47 (Table 2).

The extracts also impacted positively on the fresh and dry matter contents of the test crops. However benomyl treated plants had 7.42g and 1.50g respectively of fresh and dry matter contents which were superior to other treatments. In terms of varietal response, RMP 12 performed better attaining fresh and dry matter content of 7.98g and 1.57g respectively (Table 2). In fig. 1 the disease severity progression over the 4-week period is shown; indicating that damage to the tissues was more severe in the early weeks than the later ones.

DISCUSSION

The least disease severity observed on RMP 12 was indicative of the fact that the variety is better able to tolerate or resist the onslaught of the pathogenic fungus, *Fusarium oxysporium* responsible for wilt of groundnut. It also suggests that the variety is able to adapt very well to the humid environment and acid soils of Umudike, Southeast Nigeria noted to be strongly predisposing to *Fusarial* attacks.

The toxicity profile of the test extracts on the organism as exemplified by the disease severity scores on the groundnut plants was thus; benomyl > *D. tripetala* > *S. mombin* > sterile water. Benomyl was superior to the plant extracts in reducing the severity of the wilt disease on groundnut plant probably because it has a greater capacity to prevent the formation of mitotic spindles needed for cell growth and reproduction an ability which the extracts may not possess (Ragsdale, 1994) however plant extracts have been reported to inhibit spore germination and mycelial growth of pathogenic fungi. Though the active principles of the plant materials were not studied, plant extracts are known to contain bioactive, antimicrobial compounds such as alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, terpenoids and phenols (Amadioha, 2003; Okwu and Njoku, 2009). For example *Dennettia tripetala* contains essential oils especially oleoresin, tannins and glycosides and recently uvariopsine, dennettine and argentinine were isolated from it (Ejechi *et al.*, 1999; Janview *et al.*, 2002). Its fruits have been found to exhibit antifungal, antipesticial effects against *Fusarium* and *Aspergillus spp.*, *Rhizopus stolonifer* and *Sitophilus zeamais*. Beta-phenylnitroethane isolated from it boost its insecticidal property (Okogun and Ekong, 1969; Adedire and Akinkurolere, 2005). These compounds are known to disrupt cell membrane integrity, slow growth of hyphae and inactivate various enzymes (Okwu and Njoku; 2009; Enyiukwu and Awurum, 2011) and may have been responsible for the fungitoxic property of this test plant extract on the pathogen. In terms of overall performance of the crop, benomyl treated plants generally did better attaining fresh and dry weights of 7.42g and 1.50g respectively translating from its superior ability to check the ravages of the pathogen than the extracts. This work hence agrees with earlier finding by Awurum (2010) that *D. tripetala* extracts could be a

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viable alternative to benomyl for smallholder farm control of fungal wet rot disease of *Amaranthus sp.* in the humid Southeast, Nigeria. The superior yields of fresh and dry matter weights obtained from RMP 12 probably show that the variety could have a better genetic potential to survive and perform well in the Southeast humid environment than the other varieties. The findings of this study also supports that early control measures are necessary to forestall economic losses due to fungal attack as reported by Roberts and Urs (2003).

In conclusion, therefore RMP 12 groundnut variety could be used in farming systems of Southeast Nigeria while employing *Dennetia tripetala* extracts for fungal wilt control as an alternative to benomyl for small holder, resource-poor farmers to combat the disease, given that the extract is easily accessible in the localities, cost effective and eco-compatible.

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Fig. 1: Disease severity progress curve of the treated plants
 Sm = *Spondias mombin*, Sw = Sterile water, T = *Dennettia tripetala*, BL = Benlate (Benomyl)

Table 1: Fresh weight and dry matter yield of the three groundnut varieties

Variety	Fresh weight (g/plant)	Dry weight (g/plant)	Mean Disease severity score
Mbaise Large	6.26	1.26	3.86
Samnut 23	5.02	1.04	3.18
RMP 12	7.98	1.57	02.01
LSD (0.05)	1.59	0.36	0.73

Table 2: Effects of plant extracts on fresh weight and dry matter yield of the groundnut varieties

Plant extract	Fresh weight (g/plant)	Dry weight (g/plant)	Mean Disease severity score
Benomyl	7.42	1.50	2.28
<i>Dennettia tripetala</i>	6.36	1.34	2.98
<i>Spondias mombin</i>	5.78	1.30	3.25
Sterile water	6.10	1.21	3.47
LSD (0.05)	1.39	0.28	0.32

